

Non-Aqueous Cerimetric Determination of Organotrithiocarbonates

BALBIR CHAND VERMA and SWATANTAR KUMAR

Chemistry Department, Himachal Pradesh University, Simla-171 001

Manuscript received 31 January 1976 ; revised 21 June 1976 ; accepted 21 June 1976

The use of various chemical indicators (fuchsin, gentian violet, light green, Ferroin, methyl red, diphenylamine, malachite green, methylene blue and N,N'-diphenylbenzidine) in the redox determination of organotrithiocarbonates with ammonium hexanitratocerate (IV) in acetonitrile medium has been described. The colour-changes observed at the end-points of titrations have been tabulated. The compounds have also been titrated potentiometrically with the oxidant in acetonitrile medium using modified-calomel or antimony electrode as reference electrode and a bright platinum wire as indicator electrode.

RAO and Murty¹ were the first to describe the use of ammonium hexanitratocerate (IV) (in acetonitrile) for the determination of some organic and inorganic reductants in acetonitrile (or mixed acetonitrile-acetic acid) media. Verma and Kumar^{2,3} applied the oxidant for the visual and potentiometric determination of thiourea and its derivatives in acetonitrile. In the present investigation, the oxidant has been used for the determination of organotrithiocarbonates in acetonitrile. The compounds find applications in various fields i.e., analysis, medicine, industry and agriculture, but their determination does not appear to have attracted any attention. Since these compounds undergo decomposition with acids and alkalies, which serve as the media of a variety of aqueous redox titrations, hence the application of non-aqueous redox methods to the determination of these compounds is of great interest and scope.

The use of visual indicators (fuchsin, gentian violet, light green, ferroin, methyl red, diphenylamine, malachite green, methylene blue and N, N'-diphenylbenzidine) has been described in the direct visual titrations of organotrithiocarbonates with ammonium hexanitratocerate (IV) in acetonitrile. The potentiometric titrations have been performed using antimony or modified-calomel as reference electrode and a bright platinum wire as indicator electrode. Organotrithiocarbonates are smoothly, rapidly and quantitatively oxidised to the corresponding bis (alkyl/arylmercapto thiocarbonyl) disulphides with a single electron change.

(R=alkyl or aryl group)

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents : Potentiometric titrations were performed with 'OSAW CROMPTON' potentiometer using 'OSAW SPOT REFLECTING' galvanometer,

meter, antimony or modified calomel (methanol saturated with potassium chloride used instead of aqueous potassium chloride) reference electrode and a bright platinum wire indicator electrode.

Acetonitrile. Distilled twice from phosphorus pentoxide (5g/l).

Ammonium hexanitratocerate (IV, 0.05N in acetonitrile. Prepared by dissolving a little more than the calculated amount of dried analytical grade oxidant in acetonitrile and standardised by titration with ferrous ammonium sulphate in the presence of dilute sulphuric acid, with ferroin as indicator. The solution was stored in coloured glass stoppered bottles and kept in dry chamber.

Organotrithiocarbonates. Prepared⁴ by shaking an equimolar mixture of corresponding mercaptan, potassium hydroxide and carbon disulphide at a temperature below 10°. The compounds were recrystallised from suitable solvent mixtures and kept in a vacuum desiccator.

Indicator solutions (all in acetonitrile). fuchsin, gentian violet, light green, methyl red, malachite green, methylene blue used as 0.1% solution ; diphenylamine (0.25%) ; N, N'-diphenylbenzidine (0.05%) and ferroin (1.485g o-phenanthroline+0.695g A. R. ferrous sulphate heptahydrate in 100 ml).

Procedure : Aliquots of solutions in acetonitrile of organotrithiocarbonates were taken in a dry conical flask. The volume of the solution was made to 30 to 40 ml with the solvent and indicator solution (2 to 3 drops) added. Each solution was cooled to room temperature (25°) and titrated with standard (0.05N) ammonium hexanitratocerate (in acetonitrile) solution run from a microburette provided with a guard tube for the protection of oxidant solution from atmospheric moisture. The colour changes observed during and at the end-points of titrations of organotrithiocarbonates using various chemical indicators are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—COLOUR CHANGES OBSERVED WITH VARIOUS INDICATORS AT THE END-POINTS OF TITRATIONS OF ORGANOTRITHIOCARBONATES WITH AMMONIUM HEXANITRATOCERATE (IV) IN ACETONITRILE.

Indicator	Colour changes
Fuchsin	Straw yellow→dull red
Gentian violet	Violet→blue→green
Light green	Light green→dull red
Ferrouin	Red→deep yellow
Methyl red	Red→yellow
Diphenylamine	Straw yellow→dull red
Malachite green	Bluish green→leaf green
Methylene blue	Blue→green
N, N'-diphenylbenzidine	Red→deep blue

* 6 or 7 drops of indicator added.

The results of titrations of trithiocarbonates using these indicators agree so well that only the results with gentian violet, as a typical of the set of indicators, are recorded in Table 2.

The potentiometric titrations were performed by using a bright platinum wire indicator electrode and modified-calomel or antimony reference electrode. The solutions were magnetically stirred during potentiometric titrations. A sharp jump in potential was observed at the equivalence point in each titration. A series of potentiometric titrations was performed with different amounts of each compound using platinum-modified calomel as well as platinum-antimony electrode assembly.

The potentiometric titration curve for one of the listed trithiocarbonates as typical of the set, with ammonium hexanitratocerate using platinum wire indicator electrode and modified-calomel reference electrode is shown in Figure Ia. The same using platinum wire indicator electrode but antimony reference electrode is shown in Figure Ib.

From the volume of standard ammonium hexanitratocerate (IV) solution used corresponding to the equi-

TABLE 2—TITRATIONS OF ORGANOTRITHIOCARBONATES WITH STANDARD (0.05N) AMMONIUM HEXANITRATOCERATE IN ACETONITRILE

Compound	Values are mean of ten determinations with standard deviation (±)				Inflection point ⁺⁺ mV	Potential jump ⁺⁺ per 0.05 ml of 0.05N Cerium (IV) mV
	Amount found*, mg	Potentiometric method	Amount found*, mg	Potentiometric method		
Organotrithiocarbonates (potassium salts)						
Ethyl	10.03,0.047	10.00,0.030	40.09,0.081	40.06,0.064	300 to 340	300 to 350
Isopropyl	10.04,0.044	10.02,0.032	39.93,0.077	39.98,0.057	295 to 345	295 to 340
n-Propyl	9.99,0.039	9.99,0.032	40.06,0.074	40.08,0.054	290 to 340	300 to 340
Isobutyl	10.03,0.043	10.01,0.027	40.05,0.075	40.04,0.058	310 to 350	295 to 335
n-Butyl	9.97,0.045	9.96,0.028	39.94,0.076	39.93,1.061	315 to 345	300 to 325
n-Amyl	10.04,0.038	10.03,0.026	40.05,0.084	39.96,0.056	320 to 350	290 to 330
Benzyl	9.96,0.041	9.97,0.032	40.09,0.079	40.07,0.063	300 to 345	300 to 325

* Amount taken, 10 mg.

⁺Amount taken, 40 mg.

⁺⁺Range of 10 determinations

valence point in potentiometric titrations, the amount of each compound was calculated and the results are recorded in Table 2. Since the results obtained by potentiometric titrations using platinum-modified calomel electrode assembly agree closely with those obtained by using platinum-antimony electrode assembly, hence for sake of convenience, the former are recorded in Table 2. The inflection points and potential jumps corresponding to each compound are also recorded in the Table.

Results and Discussion

The use of various chemical indicators has been described for the first time in the non-aqueous redox determination of organotrithiocarbonates with ammonium hexanitratocerate (IV) solution (in acetonitrile), which has been described to be quite stable¹. These indicators show very sharp colour changes at the end-points (Table 1). For convenience sake, the results are recorded only with gentian violet indicator (Table 2). In the potentiometric titrations performed with either modified-calomel or antimony as reference electrode and a bright platinum wire as indicator electrode, the potentials attain stable values immediately on addition of

each instalment of the oxidant. A sharp jump in potential of the order of 290 to 350 mV per 0.05 ml of the 0.05 *N* oxidant solution is observed at the equivalence point using platinum-modified calomel electrode assembly. Using platinum-antimony electrode assembly however, the jump in potential is of the order of 270 to 325 mV with the addition of 0.05 ml of 0.05 *N* oxidant solution. The results recorded in Table 2 show that the overall standard deviations calculated from the pooled data of all the visual and potentiometric (using platinum-modified calomel electrode assembly) titrations performed with 10 mg of each compound are 0.042 and 0.030 respectively. For 40 mg samples, they are 0.078 and 0.059 respectively.

Organicisothiocyanates, thiocyanates of isocyanates do not cause any interference even when present in upto five fold excess in the determination of organotrithiocar-

bonates with ammonium hexanitratocerate (IV) in acetonitrile medium. Urea, ammonium thiocyanate, thioacetamide, thiosemicarbazide and amines interfere.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (India) for the award of research fellowship to one of them (S. K.).

References

1. B. KRATOCHVIL, *Rec. Chem. Prog.* 1966, 27, 260.
2. B. C. VERMA and S. KUMAR, *Talanta*, 1973, 20, 916.
3. B. C. VERMA and S. KUMAR, *Talanta*, 1976, 23, 612.
4. E. E. REID, 'Organic Chemistry of Bivalent Sulphur', Chemical Publishing Co., Inc., New York, 1962, Vol. IV. p. 178.